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VICTIMIZATION ON THE LABOUR MARKET IN THE PROCES OF GLOBALIZATION

Abstract

The Council of Europe clearly highlights the activities of women's non-governmental cooperation organization dealing with issues of implementation of the budget in the context of gender structures. The most commonly observed data are collected in relation to domestic violence, unemployment, labor market, health and education. In literature, the term “*quality of life*” is defined as a model that encompasses objective and subjective indicators, a wide range of living domains, and individual values. The authors of their theoretical research directed to the explanation of the concept of people’s victimization on the labor market, especially on women and children. They focus on poverty, homelessness, social assistance for people who are in the labor market. They point out that unemployment at a time of social crisis is not only a condition of the exercise of property and other crimes, but also deviant behaviors at all. The process of globalization is affecting all areas of social life, and thus no exception dealing with crime. In the continuous process of development of criminology within the sociological theories have emerged the globalization theories of criminality and victimization. The aim of this paper is to point out that globalization theories should not be viewed in isolation from other sociological theories and doctrines, but that one, although relatively new, contribute to the creation of complete systems of criminological doctrines in order to find the optimal social response to victimization of people in the conditions of labour market as the global phenomenon.

Key words: *victimology, labour market, globalization theories, gender budget, risk society, quality of life .*

Introduction

However, the development of the idea of norming and the realization of human rights has not ended with the adoption of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1948. In the eighties of the twentieth century, when there was economic growth in the countries of Europe, as well as in the United States, the idea of special rights of victims, of unauthorized behavior, or of those who enter the domain of the incomprehensible consequences of natural disasters was founded. With the development of victimology and critical criminology in the sociological thinking of the Western world, as well as economically empowered economies, from which a part of the budget for remedying the consequences of the victimhood process of the population could be separated, they grouped as protective objects in the domain of human rights and the right to peace, the right to development and the right to a healthy environment. In literature that includes sources of human rights, these rights are defined as true solidarity.

Therefore, it became necessary to isolate and protect particularly vulnerable groups of the population. Vulnerability is determined as the position of the skid with respect to the other, or fringe position in relation to the other, which take up in the company of individuals or groups of people. According to the definition of the World Health Organization, vulnerability (vulnerability) is the level at which the population, individual or organization are not able to foresee great difficulties, carry with them, resist it and recover from its impact. It is believed that these groups include: children; pregnant women; seniors; malnourished people; people with weakened immune systems, who are at particular risk in the time of adversity.

Poverty and its usual consequences, such as malnutrition, homelessness, poor housing conditions, abandonment, is the main cause of vulnerability.¹ UNESCO as a vulnerable group stands out: in the first place illiterate women; then, the young people who are not included in the training system and which have a basic literacy; prisoners; refugees, indigenous people.

The importance of the term *quality of life*

In literature, the term “*quality of life*” is defined as a model that encompasses objective and subjective indicators, a wide range of living domains, and individual values. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines the quality of life as individuals’ perception about their position in life, in the context of culture and value system they live in, and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and interests. It is a broad concept, influenced by a complex set of elements: one’s physical health, psychological status, level of independence, social contacts,

¹ World Health Organization. *Vulnerable groups*.

http://www.who.int/environmental_health_emergencies/vulnerable_groups/en/, Accessed: 26.5.2018.

personal beliefs, and relations between these elements, all of which influence the creation of a final, visible form of living standard in an individual's environment.²

There are several aspects of the quality of life, which are examined and measured separately. They may refer to: health status; work and life balance; education and skills; social ties; participation in social life and management; environmental quality; personal security; and subjective well-being. In 2011, the the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) carried out an analysis of these quality of life aspects and issued a report on this matter.³

The question was driven by the dilemma whether visible or invisible reflections of labor segregation of women and children may be measured through the indicators of quality of life. It is clear that the status of women and children can be observed through all and, particularly, through specific aspects of quality of life, such as: health status, education and skills, and the quality of the environment, in particular.

Human health is one of the most valuable aspects of human life. The results of research in many countries consistently show that the respondents consider human health and employment to be the issues of highest priority and impact on their living standard and conditions. Human health is important *per se* but also it is also essential for attaining other dimensions of human well-being, such as: a good job and good earnings, opportunities for citizens to fully participate in community life, socialize with others, get relevant education (including adult education), etc.

In relation to different political structures, or health systems of individual countries, people with lower levels of income or education are likely to be subject to higher mortality or morbidity (OECD, 2010), due to their exposure to more serious living and working conditions, inadequate health care and higher rate of unhealthy lifestyle (e.g. higer incidence of smoking or obesity), and reduced access to adequate health care.⁴

The issue of women and children education and skills directly affects their work segregation. Education is an essential need and an important human pursuit. It has a strong impact on the quality of human life and general welfare. Better educated individuals earn more, and are more likely to get employed. They live longer, have better health, and are less likely to suffer from chronic diseases, or to have some disabilities. Better educated people more actively participate in the political life of their immediate community; they are more likely to commit crime and they are less

² WHOQOL, *Measuring Quality of Life*, 1997 p. 1.

http://www.who.int/mental_health/media/68.pdf, Accessed: 23.3.2014.

³ OECD. (2011) *Compendium of OECD Well-Being*. <http://www.oecd.org/std/47918063.pdf> π Accessed 2.4.2014.

⁴ OECD. (2011) *Compendium of OECD Well-Being*, p.20.

<http://www.oecd.org/std/47918063.pdf> π Accessed 2.4.2014.

frequently the beneficiaries of social support and assistance programs. At the level of the society as a whole, better education leads to an increase in the GDP, a better tax collection and lower social spending.

Education and economic status also influence the support of social networks. Over 90% of people with secondary or higher education can count on someone for emergency assistance, as compared to only 72% of those with only elementary education. There are similar differences between people with upper and lower income levels: a fifth (92%) of the best-paid respondents reported having someone they can count on, as compared to 73% of respondents at the bottom of the income scale.⁵

The right to participate in political life is not only part of the universally guaranteed fundamental freedoms and rights; it also increases the responsibility and efficiency of public policy. In turn, it has a strong impact on human well-being, whereas public policy has a strong impact on individual lives, for example, by ensuring the provision of public services, regulation of various institutions and markets, the justice system, etc.⁶

The quality of life can also be observed through subjective safety indicators: fear, concern about crime, and the risk of crime. The debate at the international level on the role of fear, victimization, degradation of the social environment and the environment ensuring human well-being, as well as the existence of multiple methods of measuring fear, is a complex issue and points to the necessity of a multidisciplinary approach to the phenomenon of "safety perception". Previous scientific studies have established that a one-way link between individual victimization and the fear of crime does not exist; the perception of insecurity (or lack of safety) is also caused by general anxiety, which is related to individual and social variables (such as: age, sex, gender, economic conditions, cultural potentials and social networking).⁷

⁵ OECD. (2011) *Compendium of OECD Well-Being*. p. 26.

<http://www.oecd.org/std/47918063.pdf> π Accessed 2.4.2014.

⁶ OECD. (2011) *Compendium of OECD Well-Being*. p. 30.

<http://www.oecd.org/std/47918063.pdf> π Accessed 2.4.2014.

⁷ Federici, A., Muratore, M.G., Squillante, D. (2012) The Quality of Life Measured Through the Subjective Indicators of Safety: *Fear, Worry About Crime and the Risk of Criminality*, Quality of life in Italy , Social Indicators Research Series Volume 48, pp 135-150, http://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007%2F978-94-007-3898-0_8, Accessed 23, March, 2014.

OECD. (2011) *Compendium of OECD Well-Being*. p. 34.

<http://www.oecd.org/std/47918063.pdf> π Accessed 2.4.2014.

Globalization and risk society

The use of the word globalization, in the daily speech of citizens, representatives of government and politicians, scientists, often takes the significance of a stronghold for their for or against arguments, in relation to the perception they represent. Globalization is a process of interaction and integration between human beings, companies, governments of different countries, a process that takes place through international trade and investment, and is supported by information technology.⁸ The process of globalization influences: the natural environment; culture; political systems; economic development and prosperity; as well as the physical well-being of people in societies around the world.

Globalization is not a special novelty. Thousands of years ago, first of all, people, and then businesses, bought and sold goods among themselves, in different countries and at great distances. However, political and technological development in recent decades has spurred growth in cross-border trade, investment and migration of the population, to such an extent that it is often discussed about a quality new phase in the development of human society. Exact numerical data show that since 1950, the volume of world trade has grown by at least twenty times more than before, and that in just two years, from 1997-1999, foreign investment doubled at a global level, from \$ 468 trillion to \$ 827 trillion. The economic systems of free markets contributed to this progress, which have broadly developed their own creative possibilities, unassumed by closed Greek, which enables the development of trade in goods, services and investments.⁹

Being in the world of globalization processes implies living in a global "risky society". This phenomenon was dealt with by sociologist Ulrich Beck, arguing that the risky society was "an inevitable structural situation in advance of industrialization"¹⁰ and that, according to Gidens, (2005) "not limited to risks to health and the environment - it involves a whole series of related changes in contemporary social life (...) ", " so that his risks are not spatially, temporally or socially limited".¹¹

Therefore, a risky society, as Jarvis points out, analyzing Beck's learning, in fact involves much wider collectivity in terms of creating socially undesirable consequences. This includes the rise of "wicked social activities and criminal deviant

⁸ *What is Globalization*, <http://www.globalization101.org/what-is-globalization/> Accessed 6, August 2014.

⁹ *Ibid.*

¹⁰ Beck, U. Living in the world risk society. *Economy and Society Volume 35 Number 3 August 2006 (329-345)*, p. 333, from <http://hudson2.skidmore.edu/~rscarce/Soc-Th-Env/Env%20Theory%20PDFs/Beck--WorldRisk.pdf> Accessed 13, August 2014.

¹¹ Gidens, E. *Sociologija*, [Sociology], Ekonomski fakultet, Beograd, 2005, p. 73.

behavior, which leads to the breakdown of civil society in certain parts of it, the ghettoization of individuals and creates socially dysfunctional classes of individuals and increases the risk to others to increase the level of crime or personal security risk".¹²

Crime management and risk society

As the picture of crime in contemporary society changes, inevitably there is a change in the sphere of social control and order, but also in the field of criminological research and theory. Contemporary criminality, as well as social responses to it, is almost impossible to explain without taking into account the broader, globalization processes, so the explanations of criminality in which these processes occupy a central place have developed. In addition to globalization, key theoretical concepts, which are at the same time the key points of intersection of criminological research and the wider domain of social and political action in contemporary society, are also the concepts of crime management and risk society,¹³ which are further operationalized through several globalization theories of criminality. The closest link to the process of globalization is the concept of transnational organized crime. It relies heavily on the sociological concept of globalization, which signifies the way in which the world is transformed into a unified global system, and the way in which the world is narrowed by the introduction of new technology, the expansion of international trade and the international division of labor.¹⁴

The process of globalization and its impact on crime, in contemporary criminological theory, were mostly dealt with by criminologists of sociological orientation. This is understandable, because it is one of the most important social processes that is shaped by the modern world and relationships in it. Zigmund Bauman, a well-known theoretician of globalization, thinks that "global design" is one of the most significant features of our time. As such, globalization has become a central place in social sciences, as well as in the media and in political debates. In addition to Bauman, two significant globalization theorists are Back and Giddens. Giddens believes that "globalization can be defined as the reinforcement of social connections around the world that connect distant sites in such a way that local events are shaped by events that happen to miles and miles far and wide." Globalization is

¹² Jarvis, D. Ulrich Beck, *Globalization and the Rise of the Risk Society: A Critical Exegetic Analysis*. Lee Kuan Yew School of public Policy, National University of Singapore: *Research Paper Series: LKYSPP08-003*, 2008, p. 11, Accessed 6, August 2014, from http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1162662

¹³ Konstantinović-Vilić, S., Nikolić-Ristanović, V., Kostić.M. *Kriminologija*, [Criminology], Centar za publikacije Pravnog fakulteta u Nišu, Niš, 2012, p. 330.

¹⁴ Konstantinović-Vilić, S., Nikolić-Ristanović, V., Kostić.M., *Kriminologija*, [Criminology], Pelikan print, Niš, 2009. p.194.

not a phenomenon that happens "out there".¹⁵ This is not just a process that implies the impact of distant events and relations between states, but we must bear in mind that its effects are perceived and felt by all sites that can no longer isolate themselves from events and processes that occur elsewhere.¹⁶ Also, Gidens believes that the policy of emancipation is a policy of chance. Unlike her, life policy radically changes the parameters of social values, both at the individual and at the collective level. It is a self-occupation policy in a reflexively arranged environment, where reflexivity links individuality to a global whole.¹⁷ Therefore, understanding the process of globalization is necessary for understanding modern forms of crime, both national and international, because one of the products itself is the globalization and globalization of criminality.

Criminologists, studying the phenomenon of globalization of criminality, seek to find an answer to the question of which social factors influence the development of organized forms of transnational criminality. Castels thinks there is a great tension between the phenomena that are being fought at the local level and their meanings, which are being formed at the national level. The shifting of responsibility to combat transnational crime only at the level of individual countries would mean an unjustified and unrealistic burden on the countries themselves. Network-type criminal networks can undermine the state's foundations by their criminal activities. Because of this, criminal networks become the subject of contemporary criminology, especially regarding the issue of effectiveness of crime control.¹⁸ Changing the distribution of wealth in certain urban areas can lead to changes in the structure of crime, but it must be ensured that the relationship between these two phenomena is not too simplistic. Although the appearance of certain forms of crime is influenced by events in the whole of the rest of the world, they still remain largely shaped by certain local influences.

Globalization Theories on Crime

As well noted by Loder and Sparks, the issues of security and order are currently rapidly and radically changed, and it is certain that criminology can not deal with this new topic in the old way. Intellectually serious, world-wide criminology for the 21st century will be the one that seeks, conceptually, empirically

¹⁵ Gidens, E., *op. cit.*, p. 65.

¹⁶ Loeder, I., Sparks R., Contemporary landscape of crime, order and control governance, risk and globalization, in: *The Oxford Handbook of Criminology*, Oxford University Press, 2005, p. 97.

¹⁷ Giddens, A. „Modernity and self-identity. Self and society in the late modern age“, Cambridge (Polity Press), 1991, p. 24.

¹⁸ Konstantinović-Vilić, S., Nikolić-Ristanović, V., Kostić. M., (2012), *op. cit.*, p. 331.

and normatively, to mean a normative picture of crime, order, and control.¹⁹ Having in mind the impact of globalization on crime and on some of its manifestations (especially on different forms of organized crime), one should bear in mind the importance of criminal-political measures. They depend on the ability of individual countries to actively suppress globalization processes that often lead to a sudden increase in the number of individual crimes. This is especially true in trafficking in human beings and weapons and prostitution. Despite the undoubted advantages that the process of globalization has in terms of creating the preconditions for the continuous development of society, it is quite clear that it also leads to the rise of the most complex forms of crime, which is one of the biggest problems facing contemporary criminological thought. For criminology, it is particularly important that globalization has changed the angle of view on transnational crime, taking into account the impact of industrialization and urbanization on this criminological phenomenon.²⁰ There are three basic criminological theories dealing with the impact of the globalization process on crime: the Durkheim's theory of modernization, the world system theory and the ecological theory of possibilities. In the continuation of the paper, the most important characteristics of each of the above theories will be summarized.

The Durkheim's theory of modernization is based on the concept of division of labor, industrialization, urbanization, social disorganization, anomalies of modern values and the culture of heterogeneity.²¹ The process of modernization emphasizes normative patterns, value systems and contemporary values such as universalism, individualism and orientation towards success.²² As is known, the crime is conditioned by a violation of the earlier legal order. Rapid changes in the structure of society often lead to violations of legal norms. The norms of a modern industrial society replace up to then the valid social norms of a traditional society, creating an imbalance in society. This imbalance weakens the mechanisms of formal and informal control in society.²³ In the context of the process of modernization, urbanization and migration on the village-city relation have a strong impact on the changing of traditional social norms. Industrialization actually ruins a traditional family and social values. The most prominent feature of modern norms in urban areas, while less pronounced in traditional rural areas. As a consequence, in urban

¹⁹ Konstantinović-Vilić, S., Nikolić-Ristanović, V., Kostić, M., (2012), *op. cit.*, p. 332.

²⁰ For example, see: Weiss, R.P., (2000), Introduction to "Criminal justice and globalization at the new millennium." *Social Justice* 27(2), pp. 1–15.

²¹ For example, see: Neapolitan, J.L., *Cross-National Crime: A Research Review and Sourcebook*. Greenwood Press, Westport, CN, 1997.

²² Neuman, W.L. and Berger, R.J., Competing perspectives on cross-national crime: An evaluation of theory and evidence. *The Sociological Quarterly* 29(2), 1988, pp. 281–313

²³ Barak, G., Crime and Crime Control in an Age of Globalization: A Theoretical Dissection. *Critical Criminology* 10, 2001, pp. 57–72.

areas there is an increase in anomie, social disorganization and the development of criminal subcultures.²⁴ Regardless of the significance of Dirks' theory of modernization, it can also be criticized. Criminal acts are in fact only those behaviors that society recognizes as such. This theory remained apolitical because it did not deal with the extent to which political processes in a country affected the phenomenon of crime. This theory has dealt with more internal, rather than external factors of criminality, which, in our opinion, is also its biggest disadvantage.

Marx's theory of the cause of criminality finds in the existing inequality. In globalization, she sees the cause of transnational criminality. The world system theory incorporated Marx's conflict education, but at the same time stressed the influence of economic factors in criminogenesis. The main causative elements of criminality in the theory of the world system are "the global economy and the unequal expansion of the capitalist mode of production, the international system of states, the class structure and conflict, the economic inequalities, the class nature of the state, and the spread of new ideologies."²⁵ In the context of this theory, it is particularly emphasized that colonialism is a catalyst for the uneven development of the people, and this development is compromised by the global capitalist system of free trade, as a result of this system, there are peripheral and semi-peripheral Highly developed countries, as bearers of capitalism, "rule the peripheral and semi-peripheral peoples," while these others represent a kind of "buffer zone" between developed and underdeveloped peoples. The subordinated position is the result of a hierarchy among peoples. Developed countries use natural resources of underdeveloped countries because of which the underdeveloped countries have to use the products of developed countries.²⁶ On the other hand, underdeveloped countries can not break the dependency ratio because their economies are largely dependent on short-term social and economic programs.²⁷ When it comes to criminality, this theory emphasizes that inequality of social classes is a major factor in criminogenesis. The position of the people in the global hierarchy determines the class structure of peoples, political institutions and social relations, all of which are factors that influence the phenomenon of crime. Pre-capitalist patterns of economic self-sufficiency are replaced by capitalist values. The Society is investing in legal mechanisms that would redefine ownership rights in a way that contributes to the

²⁴ See: Archer, D., Gartner, R., *Violence and Crime in Cross National Perspective*, Yale University Press, New Have, 1984.

²⁵ Neuman, W.L., Berger, R.J., *op. cit.*, p. 284.

²⁶ *Ibid.*

²⁷ Frank, A.G., *Latin America: Underdevelopment or Revolution?*, Monthly Review Press, New York, 1969.;

Sumner, C., *Crime, Justice and Underdevelopmen*, Heinemann, London, 1982.

expansion of capitalism while trying to control the growth of the urban proletariat.²⁸ This theory regards crime in conditions of political and class struggle and capitalist mode of production. Also, within this theory, crime is classified into two large groups.²⁹ The former constitute crimes committed by capitalists and leading classes. These crimes are called criminals known as crimes of repression or domination. The second group of offenses are "crimes of survival". Between these two groups of criminal offenses there is clear conditionality because the crimes of repression endanger the lower social strata whose members then commit crimes to survive. The main disadvantage of Marx's system theory is that he does not take into account internal political-economic relations in one country, but looks at them globally as factors of criminality. Marx's theory also does not explain criminality outside capitalist societies. And perhaps the biggest drawback of this theory is that it sees the social hierarchy as a static creation, and the era of globalization in which we live today shows that, on the contrary, the social hierarchy is highly variable and can not be treated as a social constant.

Finally, the third in a series of globalization theories of crime is an ecological theory of possibilities. This theory explains the emergence of transnational criminality by the existence of societies that have difficulty accessing material goods, which creates opportunities for non-sanctioned unlawful behavior.³⁰ The crime rate is increasing when "a social surplus is created that increases the amount of material goods that can be stolen".³¹ At the same time, the mobility of the population increases, and the mechanisms of social control remain static, which as a result also has an increase in crime. A close-knit theory of rational choice,³² according to which the perpetrator, when deciding to commit an offense, calculates with the benefits and harm that such behavior can bring him. The greater the benefit from the commission of the crime, the greater the likelihood that it actually comes to that.

²⁸ Chambliss, W., *Functional and Conflict Theories of Crime: The Heritage of Emile Durkheim and Karl Marx.* Pp. 1-28 *Who's Law? What Order?* Eds. W.J. Chambliss and M. Mankoff. New York : Wiley, 1976; Dodd, D., "The Role of Law in Plantation Society: Reflections on the Development of a Caribbean Legal System." *International Journal of Sociology of Law* 7, 1979, pp. 275-96.

²⁹ Quinney, R., *Class, State, and Crime.* Mckay, New York, 1977.; Barak, D., *loc. cit.*

³⁰ Cantor, D., K. Land., "Unemployment and Crime Rates in the Post-World War II United States." *American Sociological Review* 50, 1985, pp. 317-32; Cohen, L.E., Kluegel, J.R., Land, K.C., "Social Inequality and Criminal Victimization: An Exposition and Test of a Formal Theory." *American Sociological Review* 46, 1981, pp. 505-34; Gurr, T.R., Grabosky, P., Hula, R., *Politics of Crime and Conflict: A Comparative History of Four Cities.*: Sage, Beverly Hills, 1977.

³¹ Neuman, W.L., Berger, R.J., *op. cit.*, p. 288.

³² See: Downs, A., *An Economic Theory of Democracy.* Harper, New York, 1957.

All the theoretical points of view clearly indicate that the process of globalization is closely linked to various types of criminal behavior. Every criminological theory in which it tries to explain the causes, conditions and phenomena of criminal behavior is in a certain way ideologically colored because it starts from a certain ideological concept. As we have seen, the process of globalization is explained by class struggle in the era of the rule of Marxist teaching, while today it is increasingly interpreted by the aspirations of the developed countries to more easily reach the material goods and energies they need for further technical, technological and social development. However, the above differences are not of such a nature that they prevent further research that would further examine the impact of the globalization process on various forms of crime.

Economic victimization of women at the labour market

Man's work is one of the most important aspects of the economic, cultural, political and personal prosperity of the individual and is embodied in the overall development and progress of a community. The process of production of material and spiritual goods, in the sense of all-purpose activity of man on the creation of usable values, is realized. The work depends on the human existence and satisfaction of all other needs for its realization and development as a generic being.³³

Criminologists agree in their view that many factors, subjective and objective, affect the reporting of reluctance. Whether it is reluctant in this most comprehensive sense, objectively induced unemployment or the habit of an individual, it is difficult to generalize. Objective ties are associated with the reduction of employment opportunities, due to economic crises or restructuring of the economy and economic branches, which is why the individual is unable to suppress or directly influence the change of such a situation in society. On the other hand, expressing lack of interest in maintaining or improving their existence, due to a special psychological state or deviation in the personality structure, determines that somebody's social status is permanently unfavorable, and the person is clearly seen, in a professional sense,³⁴ as someone who possesses social incompatibility lines, as a life in the state of a permanently violent relationship in marriage, witchcraft or homelessness.

In criminological research, the basis of which is based on the methodological concept of gender equality advocacy, various forms of social disadvantage of particularly vulnerable groups, women and children, or persons with disabilities are

³³ Konstantinovic-Vilic, S., Kostic, M. *Penologija*, [*Penology*], SVEN, Niš, 2006, p. 160.

³⁴ Perovic, K. *Kriminologija*, [*Criminology*], University of Crne Gore, Podgorica, Nikšić, 1998, p. 338.

often linked to family violence.³⁵ In some segments it is also called domestic violence. Domestic violence is most often defined as any kind of physical, sexual, psychological or economic abuse that a family member is committing to another member of the family, regardless of whether such behavior is criminalized by the legal regulations and whether the perpetrator of violence has been reported to the prosecution authorities. Enforcing domestic violence leads to endangering security and trust relationships among family members and is a form of control and manifestation of power over family members.

Violence in marriage stands out as a special type of domestic violence. Most commonly, it is understood that these are physical and sexual abuse committed by the partners one above the other, irrespective of whether it was reported or discovered, whether it was the subject of criminal or misdemeanor prosecution and adjudication. In criminological literature, it is very difficult to draw the boundary between economic exploitation, political domination, psychological oppression and physical violence, because one form of violence develops a suitable ground for the next manifestation.³⁶

In the time span of the eighties and nineties of the last century were passed and adopted the most important international documents relating to the suppression of any form of violence against women and to include legally binding standards for States Parties. It is, above all, the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women. This Convention, the Optional Protocol provides for a series of measures to end discrimination against women and obligates all States that have ratified or acceded to remove all discriminatory laws and the establishment of courts and other legal institutions the effective protection of women against discrimination.

The member states of the Council of Europe clearly highlights the activities of women's non-governmental cooperation organization dealing with, among other things, issues of implementation of the budget in the context of gender structures. The most commonly observed data are collected in relation to domestic violence, unemployment, labor market, health and education. This theoretical

³⁵ Domestic violence is considered not only on the national plane of individual countries, but also on the international plane. Among the international documents containing domestic violence standards, the UN documents and the Council of Europe stand out as particularly important: the Beijing Declaration and the Platform for Action of 1995, the Declaration on the Policy of Combating Violence against Women in a Democratic Europe since 1993 year. and Recommendation of the Council of Europe 1582, Violence against women in the family since 2002. The starting point for all these international acts is that "violence against women is a manifestation of historically unequal relationships of social power between men and women, which have led to the domination and discrimination against women by men and the prevention of the full progress of women."

³⁶ Konstantinović-Vilić, S., *et al*, (2012), p. 122.

research directed to the explanation of the concept of people's victimization on the labor market, especially on women and children. They focus on poverty, homelessness, social assistance for people who are in the labor market. It is pointed out that unemployment at a time of social crisis is not only a condition of the exercise of property and other crimes, but also deviant behaviors at all. In the continuous process of development of criminology, in constant search for new explanations of the causes of crime, within the sociological theories have emerged and economic theories of criminality and victimization. The aim of this paper is to point out that economic theories should not be viewed in isolation from other sociological theories and doctrines, but that one, although relatively new, contribute to the creation of complete systems of criminological doctrines in order to find the optimal social response to victimization of people, especially women and children, in the conditions of labour market as the global phenomenon.

In addition to this document, it should be noted the adoption of the UN Declaration on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, which provides that States should improve the penal, civil, labor and administrative sanctions in domestic legislation to punish and compensate the harm done to women who are subjected to violence, and a number of other documents to prevent such actions.

Apart from domestic violence, a lack of work can affect a woman starting to live as a rogue or homeless person. Interestingly, even in the Hamurabi Code, which contains only fragmentary provisions of criminal law, paragraph 143 stipulates that if a woman is "not a good housewife, but a tramp, if she breaks up a house, she neglects her husband, she will be thrown into the water".³⁷ Vagrancy, in the context of the law prescribed, the more the woman is a form of disobedience and idleness, for which would result in poor housekeeping, rather than just structural determination of punishment for vagrancy.

On the European continent homelessness is also one of the main social issues, which requires a clear and unequivocal politically coordinated response. The most important, unified activity in solving the social and legal status of homeless people is realized by the organization FEANTSA (European Federation of National Organizations Working with the Homelessness), which developed a homelessness and homelessness typology called ETHOS (European Typology of Homelessness and Housing Exclusion). ETHOS typology is based on a conceptual understanding of the existence of three domains that constitute the word "home", and that the absence of each one in fact indicates homelessness. If a person has his / her home, it can be permanently understood as: achieving adequate housing (or space), whereby a person and his / her family have a property right (physical domain), enabling

³⁷ Jasić, S., *Zakoni starog i srednjeg vijeka*, [Laws of the Old and Middle Ages]. Belgrade, 1968, p. 37.

privacy to be maintained and enjoying certain relations with others (social domain) and possession of legal right to residence (legal domain).

The lack of any of these three determinations leads to the establishment of four concepts of homelessness, which are described as: lack of roof over the head, homelessness, unsafe housing and inadequate housing. ETHOS, then, classifies homeless people, according to how they live or what a "home" situation is. These conceptual categories include thirteen homeless people, in order to guide and implement various political procedures, such as: mapping homelessness, development, monitoring and evaluation policies, to each of them. These categories of people are those who: live hard (in the street, public spaces, for example); live in emergency accommodation (shelters or reception stations); live in shelters for homeless people; live in shelters for women (due to domestic violence); live in refugee camps; were released from criminal institutions; receive long-term social assistance; live in unsafe conditions; live under the pressure of the seizure of property by judicial means; live under threat of violence; live a temporary / unusual way of life; live in unsuitable home conditions; living surrounded by a huge number of other people.³⁸ Certain target groups are protected, each individually, by explicit request for adequate housing, through certain documents issued at the UN level, or by the International Labor Organization (ILO): workers (MOR, 1962), refugees (MOR, 1961), children (UN, 1959, 1989), women (UN, 1979), elderly workers (MOR, 1980), immigrant workers (MOR, 1990), minorities (UN, 1991, indigenous population (UN, 1993).

Conclusion

Globalization is a process that has affected almost all societies. He brought with him a number of benefits in terms of facilitating the transfer of skills and knowledge, the development of information technologies and almost unlimited opportunities for the prosperity of peoples in different fields. But, in addition, it also led to the emergence of various forms of crime that transcended national boundaries and gained transnational character. This is especially true when it comes to organized crime and certain forms of trafficking, weapons or narcotic drugs. In addition, with the development of the Internet, the operation of criminal groups and organizations has moved into the "virtual world", and its consequences are felt in the real world. In the era of globalization, special value has natural assets because they allow for economic development and information because they create a condition for acquiring new knowledge. Because of this, criminals exhibit increased technical and technological skills. High-tech training of criminals needs to oppose even greater knowledge, training and equipment of those who deal with crime (police, courts and

³⁸ETHOS - *European Typology of Homelessness and housing exclusion*, <http://www.feantsa.org/files/freshstart/Toolkits/Ethos/Leaflet/EN.pdf>, Accessed: 27.4.2010.

prosecutors). This is practically the only way that can lead to the suppression of transnational criminality, which, in fact today, does not have clearly defined boundaries.

The process of globalization has led to the growing economic dependence of small states and peoples over the highly developed countries. The poor economic situation in these countries led to an increase in unemployment, which in turn led to the emergence of "neocolonialism" which, from the former state-owned, is increasingly gaining economic character. The solution to this problem is in the same level of economic development and creation of conditions for better and more efficient cooperation between the countries in order to suppress various forms of crime. We believe that a more complete theoretical study of the process of globalization in the context of contemporary criminological theories and learning can certainly contribute to achieving this goal.

In addition, we would like to draw attention to legislation in the field of prevention of disproportionate representation of women and men in different forms and at different levels of activity and employment, where women are subject to horizontal labour segregation (given a narrower scope of duties and responsibilities than men) and vertical labour segregation (given a job of a lower rank).³⁹

The knowledge of the Serbian legal heritage as well as of the contemporary legislation is essential for modernizing the existing normative framework, developing relevant the legal standards and sanctioning the conduct that violates and/or endangers the quality of human lives.

³⁹ Baćanović, B., Rod i upravljanje otpadom: uvođenje rodne perspektive u lokalne planove upravljanja otpadom (Gender and Waste Management: Introducing gender perspective in local waste management agenda), GIZ, Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit, Beograd, 2011, p. 35.

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